

THE EFFECT OF RADIATION AND CHEMICAL REACTION ON THE DEPLETION OF THE OZONE LAYER

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ABSTRACT

A study is made of the effect of radiation and chemical reaction on the depletion of the ozone layer. An approximate solution to the governing equations is obtained following the transformations adopted by Mebine (2007). Analysis of the results show that radiation and chemical reaction do not deplete the ozone layer but the quantity of Chlorofluorocarbons and other ozone depleting gases in the atmosphere

KEYWORDS: Radiation, Chemical reaction, Ozone layer, Boussinesq approximation, chlorofluorocarbons, Grashof number.

INTRODUCTION

Ozone (O_3) is an unstable, dark blue diamagnetic gas. The colour is due to intense absorption of red light of wavelength (λ) between 557 and 602 nanometers. It also absorbs strongly in the UV region (λ 255nm). This is particularly important since there is a layer of O_3 in the upper atmosphere which absorbs harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation from the sun, thus protecting people on the Earth. Ozone is a metastable allotrope, always having a tendency to convert back into oxygen. It is a vigorous oxidizing agent, often reacting with the evolution of oxygen. Some 30km above the earth's surface, oxygen molecules can split apart by UV light from the sun.

Some of the atoms join with other oxygen molecules to form ozone.

This reaction has been of extreme importance in the maintenance of life on Earth. The reason is that ozone has the ability to absorb electromagnetic radiation, but none of them absorb ultraviolet radiation to a useful extent (Lee1996). If too much ultraviolet radiation reaches the earth, two things happen. First, the energy balance of the Earth will be upset resulting to greenhouse effect. Secondly, increased UV radiation will bring changes in the behaviour of cells in living tissue. One unpleasant outcome will be an increase in the incidence of skin cancers. In 1985 as reported by Matthews (1996) researchers noticed that a gap in the ozone layer appeared above the Antarctic and Arctic. This hole in the ozone layer was at first thought to be just one of the many fluctuations that take place in the earth's atmosphere from time to time. However, it has been shown that it is mainly due to the presence of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) gases of high industrial value reacting with ozone. When the CFCs diffuse into the ozone layer, the ozone is removed faster than it is replaced. Matthews (1996) also reported that over the last few hundred years, the amount of carbon (IV) oxide in the atmosphere has increased by 25% and that of Methane by 200%. There is no doubt that the temperature of the atmosphere has been rising. This, together with an increase in the radiation of the Earth owing to the depletion of the ozone layer is worrying. The effects on the climate could be disastrous. Among other things, patterns of rainfall and agriculture would drastically change. It is in the light of the above, that our study is being carried out with a view to critically examine the twin effect of radiation and chemical reaction quantitatively on the rate at which the ozone layer is being depleted and if possible proffer mitigating solution.

Nomenclature

ρ' = dimensionless density

V = fluid velocity

P = fluid pressure

μ = absolute viscosity
 g = acceleration due to gravity
 t = time
 T = fluid temperature
 C = fluid concentration
 a = thermal diffusivity
 q_z = radiative term
 K_r^2 = chemical reaction term
 z = coordinate
 σ = Stefan Boltzmann constant
 C_p = specific heat at constant pressure
 T_o = initial temperature
 C_o = initial concentration
 E = coefficient of volume expansion for concentration
 ε = coefficient of volume expansion for temperature
 T_∞ = reservoir temperature
 \wedge = Planck's function
 α_{K^*} = absorption coefficient
 κ^* = frequency of radiation
 ρ_∞ = reservoir density
 θ = dimensionless temperature
 Gr = free convection parameter due to temperature
 Gc = free convection parameter due to concentration
 β^2 = dimensionless thermal diffusivity
 k^2 = dimensionless chemical reaction term
 t' = dimensionless time
 z' = dimensionless coordinate
 ν = kinematic viscosity
 c' = dimensionless temperature
 α^2 = dimensionless radiation term
 Re = Reynolds number

Mathematical formulation of the problem

The basic fluid equations governing the physical model of the problem following the argument of Bestman (1985) and under the usual Boussinesq approximation are

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} + g\varepsilon(T - T_o) + gE(C - C_o) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{\rho C_p} \nabla \cdot q_z \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{\rho C_p} K_r^2 C \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 q_z}{\partial z^2} - 3\sigma^2 q_z - 16\sigma T_\infty^3 \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (4)$$

For optically thin medium with relatively low density in the spirit of Cogley *et al.*; (1968), equation (4) reduces to

$$\frac{\partial q_z}{\partial z} = 4\delta^2(T - T_\infty) \quad (5)$$

where $\delta^2 = \int_0^\infty (\alpha_{k^*} \frac{\partial \wedge}{\partial T}) dk^*$

Non-dimensional analysis

For dimensional homogeneity of the governing fluid equations, we substitute the following dimensionless quantities or expressions of the fluid variables

$$z' = \frac{Vt}{d}, \rho' = \frac{p}{\rho V^2}, \alpha^2 = \frac{4\delta^2 \rho_\infty C_\infty d^2}{\rho C_p \nu}, C' = \frac{C - C_o}{C - C_\infty}$$

$$\beta^2 = \frac{a^2 \rho t}{T_\infty}, g' = \frac{gd}{V^2}, \theta = \frac{T - T_o}{T - T_\infty}, \rho' = \frac{\rho}{\rho_\infty}, \text{Re}^{-1} = \frac{\mu}{Vd\rho}$$

$$t' = \frac{Vd}{t}, Gr = \frac{gE(T - T_o)d^3}{V^3}, Gc = \frac{gE(C - C_o)d^3}{V^3}, K^2 = \frac{\kappa_r^2 T_\infty \nu}{a^2 V^2}$$

having employed the Rayleigh's technique into equations (1), (2), (3) and (5) and further substitution of (5) into (2) as well as assuming that $\frac{1}{\rho'} \frac{\partial P'}{\partial z'} = k_p$ (a constant pressure gradient) results in

$$\frac{\partial V'}{\partial t'} = k_p + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \frac{\partial^2 V'^2}{\partial z'^2} + Gr\theta + GcC' \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t'} = \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial z'^2} - \alpha^2 \theta \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial C'}{\partial t'} = \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 C'}{\partial z'^2} - k^2 C' \quad (8)$$

Subject to the boundary conditions

$$V'(0) = 1, V(\infty) = 0$$

$$\theta(0) = 1, \theta(\infty) = 0$$

$$C'(0) = 1, C(\infty) = 0$$

METHOD OF SOLUTION

Equations (6) – (8) are non-linear equations and would require numerical solution, however, analytical solution is possible following the transformation adopted by Mebine (2007), for sufficiently large values of the time variable, that is after the initial transient have disappeared, we seek solution of equation (6) – (8) of the forms

$$\begin{aligned} V' &= V_1(z)e^{-nt'} \\ \theta &= \theta_1(z)e^{-nt'} \\ C' &= C_1(z)e^{-nt'} \end{aligned} \quad 9(a,b,c)$$

Where n is decay constant

If we put equations 9(a,b,c) into equations (2.6) – (2.8) and simplify, we get

$$-nV_1(z') = -k_p + \frac{1}{\text{Re}}V_1''(z') + Gr\theta_1(z') + GcC'(z') \quad (10)$$

$$\beta^2\theta_1''(z') - (\alpha^2 + n)\theta_1(z') = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\beta^2C_1''(z') - (k^2 + n)C_1(z') = 0 \quad (12)$$

Subject to

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(0) &= e^{nt}, V_1(\infty) = 0 \\ \theta_1(0) &= e^{nt}, \theta_1(\infty) = 0 \\ C_1(0) &= e^{nt}, C_1(\infty) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad 9(a',b',c')$$

Solution to equations (11) and (12) after imposing the boundary conditions 9(a',b',c') are

$$\theta_1 = e^{nt'} \text{Cosh}\varphi z' \quad (13)$$

$$C' = e^{nt'} \text{Cosh}\phi z' \quad (14)$$

where $\varphi = \frac{\alpha^2 + n}{\beta^2}$ and $\phi = \frac{k^2 + n}{\beta^2}$

To solve equation (10), we substitute equations (13) and (14) in equation (10) and simplify, we get

$$V_1''(z') + n \text{Re} V_1(z') = \text{Re} k_p - e^{nt'} \text{Re} Gr \text{Cosh}\varphi z' - e^{nt'} - e^{nt'} \text{Re} Gc \text{Cosh}\phi z' \quad (15)$$

The solution of equation (15) after imposing the boundary condition 9(a') is therefore

$$V_1(z') = c_1 \text{Cos}\sqrt{n \text{Re} z'} + c_2 \text{Sin}\sqrt{n \text{Re} z'} + c_3 \text{Cosh}\varphi z' + c_4 \text{Cosh}\phi z' + c_5 \quad (16)$$

where

$$c_1 = e^{nt'} + \frac{e^{nt'} \operatorname{Re} Gr}{\varphi^2 + n \operatorname{Re}} + \frac{e^{nt'} \operatorname{Re} Gc}{\phi^2 + n \operatorname{Re}} - \frac{k_p}{n}$$

$$c_2 = -\frac{k_p}{n}$$

$$c_3 = -\frac{e^{nt'} \operatorname{Re} Gr}{\varphi^2 + n \operatorname{Re}}$$

$$c_4 = -\frac{e^{nt'} \operatorname{Re} Gc}{\phi^2 + n \operatorname{Re}}$$

$$c_5 = \frac{k_p}{n}$$

To transform back, we put equations (13), (14) and equation (16) into 9(a, b, c) and the results is

$$V' = \left(c_1 \operatorname{Cos} \sqrt{n \operatorname{Re}} z' + c_2 \operatorname{Sin} \sqrt{n \operatorname{Re}} z' + c_3 \operatorname{Cosh} \varphi z' + c_4 \operatorname{Cosh} \phi z' + c_5 \right) e^{-nt'} \quad (17)$$

$$\theta = \operatorname{Cosh} \varphi z' \quad (18)$$

$$C' = \operatorname{Cosh} \phi z' \quad (19)$$

RESULTS

For numerical validation of the problem, we use

$\operatorname{Re} = 10$, $n = 0.2254$, $\operatorname{Gr} = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$, $\alpha^2 = 4, 8, 12, 16, 20$

$k_p = 2.5$, $Gc = 1, 3, 5, 7, 9$, $k^2 = 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0, 2.4$

$\beta^2 = 5$, $t' = 0.25$

Figure1. The dependence of velocity on the space coordinates with radiation increasing.

Figure2. The dependence of velocity on the space coordinates with rate of chemical reaction increasing.

Figure 3. The dependence of velocity on the space coordinates with Grashof number due to temperature increasing.

Figure 4. The dependence of velocity on the space coordinates with Grashof number due to concentration increasing.

DISCUSSION

We start our discussion by taking a look at the effect of increasing radiation as a result of heat transfer as shown in Figure1. Figure1 shows that increasing radiation brings about a decrease in the velocity, thus confirming the potency of the ozone layer as having the ability to absorb UV radiation as mentioned by Matthews (1996) and Lee (1996). Figure 2 shows that increasing the concentration of the gases that deplete the ozone layer have a minimal effect on the rate at which the ozone layer is depleted. Increasing Gr and Gc as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively, decreases the velocity of the fluid. This shows that increase in Grashof number for temperature and concentration do not increase the rate at which the ozone layer is being depleted.

CONCLUSION

The study quantitatively laid credence to the results of earlier studies that the depletion of the ozone layer is not facilitated by the concentration of the reacting gases nor the radiation as a result of heat transfer but the quantity of chlorofluorocarbons and other ozone layer depleting gases in the atmosphere.

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